

Spatial Analysis of Population Fertility Levels in Dhi Qar Governorate for the Period 2015-2025

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Abstract

The main objectives of this research are measuring and testing the level of population fertility and its distribution by the environment in administrative units of Dhi Qar Governorate. Considering several indicators of fertility, using official population estimates, the study notes that there are great differences among the various administrative units. In 2015, the Crude Birth Rate (CBR) in Dhi Qar Governorate was 20.6 live births per 1,000 population, which slightly reduced to 20.4 in 2025. The General Fertility Rate (GFR) for the study area was 86 live births per 1,000 women of reproductive age (15–49 years) in the 2 out of the 3 years of the study described above; the rate decreased to 85 in urban areas, but was still in both years in rural areas. In addition, the Child-Woman Ratio (CWR) in 2015 was 592.2 children (0–4 age) per 1,000 women (15–49 age), but was projected to slightly drop to 580.4 children per 1,000 women by 2025.

Keywords: *Population Fertility, Crude Birth Rate, Fertility Levels, Dhi Qar Governorate.*

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Introduction

The phenomenon of childbearing in any given society is called population fertility which is expressed through the number of live births. Population fertility and women's fecundity—the physiological ability to become pregnant and bear a child given normal circumstances, which varies between women, needs to be distinguished. There are a number of social, environmental and economic factors that mean different fertility levels for different populations. An inevitable consequence of having a high fertility rate is that the percentage of the young (0–14 years) increases, thereby decreasing the percentage of working-age (15–64 years) and elderly (65 years and over) people. This leads to a large base in the population pyramid and lets the society being studied to offset the loss of population through ageing and deaths. This situation at the same time is posing a challenge for a society to easily achieve the "Demographic Dividend" threshold, from which comes various benefits and advantages. Crude Birth Rate (CBR), Gross Reproduction Rate (GRR), Net Reproduction Rate (NRR), General Fertility Rate (GFR), Age-Specific Fertility Rate (ASFR), Total Fertility Rate (TFR), and Child-Woman Ratio (CWR) are the different measures of fertility. Because it was not possible to have all these indicators on official data sources, this study will cover some of the indicators.

Research Problem

The research problem is formulated using the following questions: Is there any change in the population fertility levels with regard to administrative units and environment of Dhi Qar Governorate from the period 2015–2025? Or can the measures of fertility used in this study document this diversity?

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Research Hypothesis

Two levels of variations in the population fertility levels in the administrative units and environments in Dhi Qar Governorate are assumed for 2015 and 2025. It also assumes that the indicators of fertility used in this paper are helpful in depicting a spatial gap between fertility rates at the administrative and environmental levels.

Research Objective

The main objective of the study is to illustrate and analyse the spatial and temporal changes in the fertility level at a micro level, within the boundaries of Dhi Qar Governorate.

Research Methodology

Two methods have been used: descriptive method in an effort to describe the state of the population fertility indicators in Dhi Qar Governorate, and analytical method, specifically statistical analysis, to draw conclusions from the data obtained from the relevant official authorities.

Research Boundaries

- **Temporal Boundaries:** The years 2015 and 2025.
- **Spatial Boundaries:** Dhi Qar Governorate is located in the southern part of Iraq. To its borders are five governorates: Wasit to the north, Maysan to the east, Basra to the south and southeast, Al-Qadisiyah to the northwest, and Al-Muthanna to the west and southwest. In the astronomic field, it is situated between the latitudes $30^{\circ}36'$ and 32° N, and the longitudes $45^{\circ}36'$ and $47^{\circ}12'$ E. The study area contains 20 urban centres within five urban districts where there is a wide variation in the areas of urban centres (Figure 1).

Research Structure

The research is based on the analysis of a number of population fertility indicators, which is preceded by introduction, then research results and followed by conclusions and recommendations will propose a number of solutions to the problem of research. This study concludes with the citations and references utilized.

Figure 1. Boundaries of Dhi Qar Governorate and its Administrative Units, 2025
 Source: Republic of Iraq, 2025.

First: Crude Birth Rate (CBR) The Crude Birth Rate is a basic statistic used in vital and fertility statistics. One of the more widely used and simplest metrics, because of its simple conceptualization, it has been embraced by many and its basic data is easily available. The total number of live births within the year divided by the mid-year population of the same year multiplied by (1,000). The constant of 1,000, rather than 100, is used for similar reasons, keeping the numbers sufficiently large and the number of decimals to a minimum, for easy interpretation and readability of the results.

There are a number of drawbacks, however, in implementing this measure. In some populations, the male-to-female ratio can be higher than normal, either because there are more males being born than females due to natural increase, or because the "pull" regions have mainly males migrating amongst them, thus lowering the rate. On the other hand, in societies where the number of females is greater, the rate is higher. Another criticism which detracts from the accuracy of this measure in mirroring the true demographic situation is the possibility of errors, or failure of birth registration at year end. The delay in registrations in some cases is up to the next year generating some bias into the study year and into the year to which it is registered. Normally, societies in the development process will have higher CBR while developed societies have lower CBR values because of birth control practices.

The CBR, which directly influences population fertility levels, is affected by two primary factors:

1. **Maternal Age Structure:** This is a very significant factor in the determination of the fertility level of any society. It is also able to take into account fluctuations in fertility, having a direct influence on the number of live births. The live births of women generally reach their highest average in the age group (30–39), and decrease in the lower and higher age cohorts (15–29) and (40–49).
2. **Age at Marriage:** It's also a critical factor in fertility levels and differences between and within geographies and socio-economic groups. Early marriage increases reproductive life and, hence, the total fertility. It's worth highlighting that here, it's "age at marriage" of women since the reproductive window of women is limited in nature by age, while the reproductive window of men extends into the later ages. The extent to which this factor influenced is evident in the study area as higher fertility rate among people in rural areas compared to urban ones. This is blamed on the rural social values which foster the practice of early marriage compared to urban areas where women are better educated and have access to employment, and thus marry at later ages and have a shorter reproductive span. (Al-Khafaf, & Al-Rihani, 1986)

$$\text{Crude Birth Rate} = \frac{\text{Number Of Live Births In A Given Year}}{\text{Mid-Year Population Of That Same Year}} * 1000 \quad (1)$$

which results in a reduction in the frequency of childbearing. This decline is reflected in the number of live births and, consequently, in the overall population fertility levels within those regions (1).

The Crude Birth Rate is categorized into three distinct levels:

- **High Birth Rates:** When the rate reaches 35 per 1,000 or above.
- **Moderate Birth Rates:** When the rate ranges between more than 20 per 1,000 and less than 35 per 1,000.
- **Low Birth Rates:** When the rate is 20 per 1,000 or below (2).

According to the data presented in Table 1, the number of total population in Dhi Qar Governorate was equal to 2,004,452 persons; 1,278,333 persons in urban areas and 726,119 persons in rural areas by mid-2015. Nasiriyah District ranked first with a mid-year population of 743,340, comprising 589,889 urban dwellers and 153,451 rural residents. In second place was Shatrah District with a population of 441,554: 255,323 in urban areas and 186,231 in rural regions. Rifai District had the third population of 415,192 with more population in rural area (217,664) compared to urban (197,528). Suq al-Shuyukh District recorded 306,156 residents (165,459 urban; 140,697 rural), while Chibayish District was the smallest at

98,210 persons (70,133 urban; 28,077 rural). Notably, in 2015, urban populations exceeded rural ones across all districts except for Rifai, which was predominantly rural.

By mid-2025, the population of the study area grew to 2,556,059, with 1,689,780 residing in urban centers and 866,279 in rural areas. The relative positions of districts in terms of population remained the same. Nasiriyah District continued to be leading with 962,824 people (779,754 urban; 183,070 rural), trailed by Shatrah District which had 559,681 people (337,503 urban; 222,178 rural). Rifai District had a population of 520,782 but in contrast to 2015, the urban population slightly outnumbered the rural population (261,105 and 259,677, respectively) as a result of having a greater urban population growth rate. Next came Suq al-Shuyukh District with 386,567 inhabitants (218,711 urban; 167,856 rural), and lastly Chibayish District totalled 126,203 inhabitants (92,707 urban; 33,496 rural).

Table 1. Mid-Year Population Estimates for Dhi Qar Governorate (2015 and 2025), Disaggregated by Administrative Units and Environment (Urban/Rural)

Administrative Unit	Total Population, mid-2015 (Persons)			Total Population, mid-2025 (Persons)		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total
Nasiriyah District Center	530839	0	530839	701698	0	701698
Al-Islah	15187	29243	44430	20075	34887	54962
Al-Batha	24549	22229	46778	32450	26520	58970
Sayyed Dakhil	14560	43830	58390	19247	52290	71537
Ur	4754	58148	62902	6284	69372	75656
Total	589889	153451	743340	779754	183070	962824
Al-Rifa'i District Center	70921	84402	155323	93748	100694	194442
Qalat Sukkar	50730	49377	100107	67058	58908	125966
Al-Nasr	48571	50730	99301	64205	60522	124727
Al-Fajr	27306	33154	60460	36095	39554	75649
Total	197528	217664	415192	261105	259677	520782
Suq Al-Shuyukh District Center	125074	0	125074	165328	0	165328
Akika	4365	43043	47408	5769	51352	57121
Karma Beni Said	16018	43233	59251	21173	51578	72751
Al-Fadhiliya	15796	38686	54482	20881	46154	67035
Al-Tar	4206	15735	19941	5560	18773	24333
Total	165459	140697	306156	218711	167857	386568
Al-Chibayish District Center	35430	7702	43132	46833	9188	56021
Al-Hammar	7765	1697	9462	10264	2025	12289
Al-Fuhud	26939	18678	45617	35610	22284	57894
Total	70133	28077	98210	92707	33496	126203
Al-Shatra District Center	173169	64894	238063	228906	77419	306325
Al-Dawaya	35999	49363	85362	47586	58892	106478
Al-Gharraf	46155	71974	118129	61011	85867	146878
Total	255323	186231	441554	337503	222178	559681
Governorate Total	1278333	726119	2004452	1689780	866279	2556059

Source: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization (CSO), Directorate of Population Statistics, 2015; Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization (CSO), Directorate of Population Statistics, 2025.

It is observed from Table 2 that the number of live births in the study area in 2015 reached 41,197, with rural areas accounting for 14,730 live births. At the district level, Nasiriyah District ranked first with 15,610 live births, followed by Shatrah District (8,691), Rifai District (8,598), Souq Al-Shuyoukh District (6,234), and finally Chibayish District (8,691). Regarding the environmental distribution of live births for

the same year, rural areas in the governorate recorded 4,456; 3,626; 3,184; 2,887; and 577 live births for the districts of Rifai, Shatrah, Nasiriyah, Souq Al-Shuyoukh, and Chibayish, respectively. Meanwhile, urban areas recorded 12,426 live births in Nasiriyah District, 5,085 in Shatrah, 4,142 in Rifai, 3,347 in Souq Al-Shuyoukh, and 1,487 in Chibayish.

At the level of smaller administrative units, the highest number of live births was recorded in the center of Nasiriyah District (11,256), all of which were in urban areas as the district center does not include rural areas within its boundaries. A similar case was observed in the center of Souq Al-Shuyoukh District, where the number of live births reached 2,493, all in urban areas. In contrast, the Al-Hammar sub-district, belonging to Chibayish District, recorded the lowest number of live births with 203. The remaining administrative units in the governorate fell within this range.

By 2025, the number of live births in the governorate increased to 52,026, including 34,516 in urban areas and 17,510 in rural areas. Regarding the districts, Nasiriyah remained the leader with 20,403 live births, distributed between urban (16,660) and rural areas (3,743). Shatrah District followed with 10,897 live births (6,573 urban and 4,324 rural). Rifai District ranked third with 10,695 live births (5,377 urban and 6,318 rural), followed by Souq Al-Shuyoukh with 7,379 live births (3,907 urban and 5,318 rural), and finally Chibayish District with 2,652 live births (1,934 urban and 718 rural). At the sub-district level, Nasiriyah center maintained its first-place position as in 2015 with 15,087 births, while Al-Hammar sub-district remained in the last position with 261 births.

Table 3 and Figures 1 and 2 show that the Crude Birth Rate (CBR) in Dhi Qar Governorate in 2015 was 20.6 per 1,000 population (20.7 in urban areas and 20.3 in rural areas), which is classified as a "moderate" fertility level according to the aforementioned scale. This rate decreased to 20.4 per 1,000 in 2025 but remained within the moderate level. While urban areas maintained the same rate, it dropped to 20.2 in rural areas. At the level of districts and smaller administrative units, the rate was equal or close to the governorate's average in both years, except for Shatrah District, where the rate dropped to the third level due to the low number of live births relative to its population size. Similarly, the rate decreased in the center of Souq Al-Shuyoukh District to 19.9 and 17.2 in 2015 and 2025, respectively, also occupying the third level. Conversely, the rate rose in the Al-Tar sub-district (Souq Al-Shuyoukh) to reach 23 in urban areas in 2025, likely due to the small population size of the sub-district.

Table 2. Number of Live Births in Dhi Qar Governorate (2015 & 2025) by Administrative Units and Environment

Administrative Unit	Number of Live Births, 2015 (Persons)			Number of Live Births, 2025 (Persons)		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total
Nasiriyah District Center	11256	0	11256	15087	0	15087
Al-Islah	311	601	912	426	721	1147
Al-Batha	504	483	987	641	523	1164
Sayyed Dakhil	268	899	1167	387	1088	1475
Ur	87	1201	1288	119	1411	1530
Total	12426	3184	15610	16660	3743	20403
Al-Rifa'i District Center	1501	1734	3235	1934	2089	4023
Qalat Sukkar	1073	1027	2100	1354	1207	2561
Al-Nasr	1005	1012	2017	1366	1221	2587
Al-Fajr	563	683	1246	723	801	1524
Total	4142	4456	8598	5377	5318	10695
Suq Al-Shuyoukh District Center	2493	0	2493	2851	0	2851
Akika	89	903	992	129	1042	1171
Karma Beni Said	364	884	1248	428	1026	1454
Al-Fadhiliya	317	778	1095	436	940	1376
Al-Tar	84	322	406	128	399	527

Total	3347	2887	6234	3972	3407	7379
Al-Chibayish District Center	744	172	916	1017	199	1216
Al-Hammar	164	39	203	202	59	261
Al-Fuhud	579	366	945	715	460	1175
Total	1487	577	2064	1934	718	2652
Al-Shatra District Center	3401	1287	4688	4476	1524	6000
Al-Dawaya	763	937	1700	918	1137	2055
Al-Gharraf	901	1402	2303	1179	1663	2842
Total	5065	3626	8691	6573	4324	10897
Governorate Total	26467	14730	41197	34516	17510	52026

Source: Based on: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Health, Directorate General of Dhi Qar Health, Unpublished Data, 2025.

Table 3. Crude Birth Rate (CBR) of the Population in Dhi Qar Governorate (2015 & 2025) by Administrative Units and Environment

Administrative Unit	Crude Birth Rate (CBR), 2015 (Persons)			Projected Crude Birth Rate (CBR), 2025 (Persons)		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total
Nasiriyah District Center	21.2	0	21.2	21.5	0	21.5
Al-Islah	20.5	20.6	20.5	21.2	20.7	20.9
Al-Batha	20.5	21.7	21.1	19.8	19.7	19.7
Sayyed Dakhil	18.4	20.5	20.0	20.1	20.8	20.6
Ur	18.3	20.7	20.5	18.9	20.3	20.2
Total	21.1	20.7	21.0	21.4	20.4	21.2
Al-Rifa'i District Center	21.2	20.5	20.8	20.6	20.7	20.7
Qalat Sukkar	21.2	20.8	21.0	20.2	20.5	20.3
Al-Nasr	20.7	19.9	20.3	21.3	20.2	20.7
Al-Fajr	20.6	20.6	20.6	20.0	20.3	20.1
Total	21.0	20.5	20.7	20.6	20.5	20.5
Suq Al-Shuyukh District Center	19.9	0	19.9	17.2	0	17.2
Akika	20.4	21.0	20.9	22.4	20.3	20.5
Karma Beni Said	22.7	20.4	21.1	20.2	19.9	20.0
Al-Fadhiliya	20.1	20.1	20.1	20.9	20.4	20.5
Al-Tar	20.0	20.5	20.4	23.0	21.3	21.7
Total	20.2	20.5	20.4	18.2	20.3	19.1
Al-Chibayish District Center	21.0	22.3	21.2	21.7	21.7	21.7
Al-Hammar	21.1	23.0	21.5	19.7	29.1	21.2
Al-Fuhud	21.5	19.6	20.7	20.1	20.6	20.3
Total	21.2	20.6	21.0	20.9	21.4	21.0
Al-Shatra District Center	19.6	19.8	19.7	19.6	19.7	19.6
Al-Dawaya	21.2	19.0	19.9	19.3	19.3	19.3
Al-Gharraf	19.5	19.5	19.5	19.3	19.4	19.3
Total	19.8	19.5	19.7	19.5	19.5	19.5
Governorate Total	20.7	20.3	20.6	20.4	20.2	20.4

Source: Based on Tables 1 and 2.

Figure 2. Crude Birth Rate (CBR) of the Population in Dhi Qar Governorate (2015) by Administrative Units and Environment
 Source: Prepared by the author based on Table 3

Figure 3. Crude Birth Rate (CBR) of the Population in Dhi Qar Governorate (2025) by Administrative Units and Environment
 Source: Prepared by the author based on Table 3

Second: General Fertility Rate (GFR)

The General Fertility Rate is considered a more precise measure than the Crude Birth Rate because it adjusts the denominator of the mathematical formula to a more specific population. It compares the number of live births solely to females of reproductive age, excluding all males and females outside the childbearing years. So, this rate adjusts for differences in population levels in different areas, for differences in sex ratios within each community and almost completely removes effects from migration, especially male-dominated migration. The GFR would be calculated as total number of live births divided by the mid-year population of females of reproductive age group, typically the (15–49) age group, then multiplied by (1,000).

The mathematical formula for calculating this rate is:

$$\text{GFR} = \frac{B_t}{F(15-49)} * 1000 \quad (2)$$

Where:

- GFR: General Fertility Rate.
- B_t : Total number of live births during a specific year.
- $F(15-49)$: Number of females in the reproductive age group at mid-year.

Statistical Analysis of Reproductive-Age Females

The analysis of the reproductive-age females was done statistically to understand the reproductive capacity of the females. From Table (4) and Figures (3 and 4), it is observed that in the study area 481,265 were females of reproductive age of 15–49 in 2015. Females dropped to 171,462 in rural areas while females increased at 309,803 in urban areas.

At the district level, Nasiriyah District ranked first with 179,194 females (142,959 urban; 36,235 rural), followed by Al-Shatra District with 105,853 (61,877 urban; 43,976 rural). Al-Rifa'i District ranked third with 99,269 (47,871 urban; 51,398 rural), followed by Suq Al-Shuyukh District in fourth place with 73,322 (40,099 urban; 33,223 rural). Finally, Al-Chibayish District recorded 23,627 (16,997 urban; 6,630 rural). At the sub-district level, the highest concentration was recorded in Nasiriyah Center with 128,648 females, all within urban areas. Conversely, the lowest number was in Al-Hammar Sub-district (Al-Chibayish District) with 2,283 females (1,882 urban; 401 rural).

By 2025, the number of reproductive-age females in Dhi Qar Governorate rose to 607,951, distributed between 404,586 in urban areas and 203,365 in rural areas. Nasiriyah District maintained its leading position with 229,674 females (186,697 urban; 42,977 rural), followed by Al-Shatra with 132,967 (80,809 urban; 52,158 rural). Al-Rifa'i recorded 123,478 (62,517 urban; 60,961 rural), while Suq Al-Shuyukh reached 91,772 (52,366 urban; 39,406 rural), and Al-Chibayish recorded 30,060 (22,197 urban; 7,863 rural). The highest concentration remained in Nasiriyah Center with 168,008 urban females, while the lowest remained in Al-Hammar Sub-district with 2,933 females (2,458 urban; 475 rural).

Table 4. Number of Females of Reproductive Age in Dhi Qar Governorate (Mid-2015 & Mid-2025) by Administrative Units and Environment

Administrative Unit	Number of women of childbearing age, mid-year 2015 (Person)			Estimated female population of childbearing age, mid-2025		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total
Nasiriyah District Center	128648	0	128648	168008	0	168008
Al-Islah	3681	6905	10586	4807	8190	12997

Al-Batha	5949	5249	11198	7770	6226	13996
Sayyed Dakhil	3529	10350	13879	4608	12275	16883
Ur	1152	13731	14883	1505	16286	17791
Total	142959	36235	179194	186697	42977	229674
Al-Rifa'i District Center	17188	19930	37118	22446	23639	46085
Qalat Sukkar	12294	11660	23954	16056	13829	29885
Al-Nasr	11771	11979	23750	15373	14208	29581
Al-Fajr	6618	7829	14447	8642	9286	17928
Total	47871	51398	99269	62517	60961	123478
Suq Al-Shuyukh District Center	30312	0	30312	39585	0	39585
Akika	1058	10164	11222	1381	12055	13436
Karma Beni Said	3882	10209	14091	5069	12108	17177
Al-Fadhiliya	3828	9135	12963	5000	10835	15835
Al-Tar	1019	3716	4735	1331	4407	5738
Total	40099	33223	73322	52366	39406	91772
Al-Chibayish District Center	8586	1819	10405	11213	2157	13370
Al-Hammar	1882	401	2283	2458	475	2933
Al-Fuhud	6529	4411	10940	8526	5231	13757
Total	16997	6630	23627	22197	7863	30060
Al-Shatra District Center	41967	15324	57291	54807	18175	72982
Al-Dawaya	8724	11656	20380	11394	13825	25219
Al-Gharraf	11186	16996	28182	14608	20158	34766
Total	61877	43976	105853	80809	52158	132967
Governorate Total	309803	171462	481265	404586	203365	607951

Source: Based on: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Health, Dhi Qar Health Directorate, Unpublished Data, 2025.

Analysis of Table (5) reveals that the General Fertility Rate (GFR) in Dhi Qar Governorate remained consistent between 2015 and 2025, standing at **86 live births per 1,000 women of reproductive age**. This stability was also observed in the governorate's rural areas for both years, whereas the rate slightly decreased to **85** in urban areas during the same period.

District-Level Variations (2015–2025)

In 2015, the districts of Nasiriyah, Rifai, and Chibayish recorded the highest fertility rates at 87 live births per 1,000 women. In contrast, the rate declined to 85 in Suq al-Shuyukh District and reached its lowest point in Shatrah District at 82.

By 2025, the demographic landscape shifted as follows:

- Nasiriyah District: Ranked first with an increased rate of 89.
- Chibayish District: Ranked second with a rate of 88.
- Rifai District: Ranked third, maintaining a rate of 87.
- Shatrah District: Ranked fourth at 82.
- Suq al-Shuyukh District: Ranked fifth and last, with the rate dropping to 80.

Sub-District Analysis (2015)

For smaller administrative units, the highest GFR in 2015 was recorded in Al-Hamma sub-district (Chibayish District) at 89 live births per 1,000 women; specifically, 87 in urban areas and the highest was in rural sectors which was 97 live births per 1,000 women. On the other hand, the lowest fertility rate (82) was found in the centers of the following sub-districts: Suq al-Shuyukh, Shatrah, and Al-Gharraf

sub-district. A range of between the above has been observed in fertility rates of other administrative units.

Figure 4. General Fertility Rate (GFR) in Dhi Qar Governorate (2015) by Administrative Units and Environment

Source: Prepared by the author based on Table 5

Figure 5. General Fertility Rate (GFR) in Dhi Qar Governorate (2025) by Administrative Units and Environment

Source: Prepared by the author based on Table 5

Table 5. General Fertility Rate (GFR) in Dhi Qar Governorate (2015 & 2025) by Administrative Units and Environment

Administrative Unit	2015			2025		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total
Nasiriyah District Center	87	0	87	90	0	90
Al-Islah	84	87	86	89	88	88
Al-Batha	85	92	88	82	84	83
Sayyed Dakhil	76	87	84	84	89	87
Ur	76	87	87	79	87	86
Total	87	88	87	89	87	89
Al-Rifa'i District Center	87	87	87	86	88	87
Qalat Sukkar	87	88	88	84	87	86
Al-Nasr	85	84	85	89	86	87
Al-Fajr	85	87	86	84	86	85
Total	87	87	87	86	87	87
Suq Al-Shuyukh District Center	82	0	82	72	0	72
Akika	84	89	88	93	86	87
Karma Beni Said	94	87	89	84	85	85
Al-Fadhiliya	83	85	84	87	87	87
Al-Tar	82	87	86	96	91	92
Total	83	87	85	76	86	80
Al-Chibayish District Center	87	95	88	91	92	91
Al-Hammar	87	97	89	82	124	89
Al-Fuhud	89	83	86	84	88	85
Total	87	87	87	87	91	88
Al-Shatra District Center	81	84	82	82	84	82
Al-Dawaya	87	80	83	81	82	81
Al-Gharraf	81	82	82	81	82	82
Total	82	82	82	81	83	82
Governorate Total	85	86	86	85	86	86

Source: Calculated by the author based on Tables 2 and 4

Third: Child-Woman Ratio (CWR)

Child-Woman Ratio is the number of children in the (0–4) age group per one thousand women of reproductive age (15–49). Child mortality should be included in this age group (0–4 years), as high mortality rates can negatively impact the calculated ratio. Unless adjusted, it might be less reliable in reflecting changes in the level of fertility over the preceding five years.

The mathematical formula for calculating this ratio is:

$$CWR = \frac{p_{0-4}}{F_{15-49}} * 100 \quad (3)$$

Where:

- p_{0-4} : Total number of children under 5 years of age.
- F_{15-49} : Total number of women in the reproductive age group (15–49 years).

Statistical Distribution of the Child-Woman Ratio

According to Table (6), the number of children in the (0–4) age group in Dhi Qar Governorate in 2015 reached 285,011. Urban areas accounted for 169,937 children, while rural areas accounted for 115,074.

At the district level, Nasiriyah District ranked first with 102,736 children, followed by Al-Shatra District with 63,455, and Al-Rifa'i District with 60,754. Suq Al-Shuyukh District ranked fourth with 44,292 children, followed by Al-Chibayish District with 13,773.

Regarding the environmental distribution of children in the (0–4) age group for the same year, rural areas in the governorate's districts recorded the following figures: 24,318 in Nasiriyah, 34,495 in Al-Rifa'i, 22,297 in Suq Al-Shuyukh, 4,450 in Al-Chibayish, and 29,513 in Al-Shatra.

Urban areas recorded 78,418; 26,259; 21,995; 9,323; and 33,942 children for the districts of Nasiriyah, Al-Rifa'i, Suq Al-Shuyukh, Al-Chibayish, and Al-Shatra, respectively. At the sub-district level, Nasiriyah Center ranked first with 70,568 children, while Al-Hammar Sub-district ranked last with 1,301 children; the remaining sub-districts fell within the range between these two values.

By 2025, the total number of children in the (0–4) age group in Dhi Qar Governorate reached 352,840, distributed between urban areas (218,264) and rural areas (134,576). At the district level, Nasiriyah District maintained its first-place ranking with 129,158 children, including 100,718 in urban areas and 28,440 in rural areas. Al-Chibayish District ranked last with 17,179 children, including 11,975 in urban areas and 5,262 in rural areas, while other districts fell within this range.

At the sub-district level, the rankings remained consistent with the 2015 data; Nasiriyah Center secured the first position with 90,636 children, while Al-Hammar Sub-district remained in the last position with 1,641 children, with all other administrative units distributed between these two figures.

Table 6. Number of Children in the (0–4) Age Group in Dhi Qar Governorate (2015 & 2025) by Administrative Units and Environment

Administrative Unit	2015			2025		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total
Nasiriyah District Center	70568	0	70568	90636	0	90636
Al-Islah	2019	4634	6653	2593	5420	8013
Al-Batha	3263	3523	6786	4191	4120	8311
Sayyed Dakhil	1936	6946	8882	2486	8123	10609
Ur	632	9215	9847	812	10777	11589
Total	78418	24318	102736	100718	28440	129158
Al-Rifa'i District Center	9428	13376	22804	12109	15643	27752
Qalat Sukkar	6744	7825	14569	8662	9151	17813
Al-Nasr	6457	8040	14497	8293	9402	17695
Al-Fajr	3630	5254	8884	4662	6145	10807
Total	26259	34495	60754	33726	40341	74067
Suq Al-Shuyukh District Center	16627	0	16627	21355	0	21355
Akika	580	6821	7401	745	7978	8723
Karma Beni Said	2129	6851	8980	2735	8013	10748
Al-Fadhiliya	2100	6131	8231	2697	7170	9867
Al-Tar	559	2494	3053	718	2916	3634
Total	21995	22297	44292	28250	26077	54327
Al-Chibayish District Center	4710	1221	5931	6049	1427	7476
Al-Hammar	1032	269	1301	1326	315	1641
Al-Fuhud	3581	2960	6541	4600	3462	8062
Total	9323	4450	13773	11975	5204	17179

Al-Shatra District Center	23020	10284	33304	29567	12027	41594
Al-Dawaya	4786	7823	12609	6147	9149	15296
Al-Gharraf	6136	11406	17542	7881	13339	21220
Total	33942	29513	63455	43593	34515	78108
Governorate Total	169937	115074	285011	218264	134576	352840

Sources: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization (CSO), Directorate of Population Statistics, 15; Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization (CSO), Directorate of Population Statistics, 2025.

Table 7 and Figures 5 and 6 indicate that the Child-Woman Ratio (CWR) in Dhi Qar Governorate in 2015 was 592.2 children per 1,000 women. This ratio was 548.5 in urban areas and 371.4 in the governorate's rural areas. At the district level, Rifai District ranked first with a ratio of 612 (548.5 in urban and 720.6 in rural areas), followed by Souq Al-Shuyoukh District at 604.1 (548.5 urban and 556 rural), then Shatrah District at 599.5 (548.5 urban and 477 rural). Chibayish District ranked fourth with a ratio of 582.9 (548.5 urban and 261.8 rural), and finally, Nasiriyah District at 573.3. The lower ratio in Nasiriyah is attributed to its large population size, which increased the number of women in the 15–49 age group, consequently affecting the child-woman ratio (548.5 urban and 170.1 rural). At the sub-district level, Al-Gharraf sub-district ranked first with the highest ratio of 622.5 (548.5 in its urban center and 723.7 in its rural areas). Conversely, the centers of Nasiriyah and Souq Al-Shuyoukh districts recorded the lowest ratios, both standing at 548.5.

By 2025, the Child-Woman Ratio in Dhi Qar Governorate decreased to 580.4. In urban areas, it declined to 539.5, whereas it rose to 661.7 in rural areas. At the district level, Rifai District maintained its first-place ranking with 599.8 (539.5 urban and 661.8 rural), followed by Souq Al-Shuyoukh at 592 (539.5 urban and 661.8 rural), then Shatrah at 587.4 (539.5 urban and 661.7 rural). Chibayish District followed with 571.5 (539.5 urban and 661.8 rural), and Nasiriyah District remained last with 562.4 (539.5 urban and 661.7 rural). Regarding the smaller administrative units, the centers of Nasiriyah and Souq Al-Shuyoukh districts ranked last with the lowest ratio of 539.5. In contrast, Ur sub-district (Nasiriyah District) moved to first place with a ratio of 651.4 (539.5 in its rural areas and 661.7 in its urban areas). The remaining administrative units in the study area fell within the range between these values.

Figure 6. Child-to-woman ratio in Dhi Qar Governorate (2015) by administrative units and environment

Source: Based on Table 7

Figure 7. Child-to-Woman Ratio in Dhi Qar Governorate (2025) by Administrative Units and Environment

Source: Based on Table 7

Conclusions

The Crude Birth Rate (CBR) in Dhi Qar Governorate reached 20.6 per 1,000 population in 2015, with 20.7 in urban areas and a lower rate of 20.3 in rural areas. By 2025, this rate decreased to 20.4 per 1,000 for the entire governorate, with 20.4 and 20.2 recorded in urban and rural areas, respectively.

The General Fertility Rate (GFR) in the study area was 86 live births per 1,000 women of reproductive age (15–49 years) in both 2015 and 2025, a stability also observed in rural areas. However, this rate declined to 85 in urban regions.

The Child-to-Woman Ratio (CWR) in 2015 was 592.2 children (aged 0–4 years) per 1,000 women (aged 15–49 years) for the whole study area. It stood at 548.5 in urban areas and 371.4 in rural areas. By 2025, the governorate-wide ratio decreased to 580.4. While the urban ratio also fell to 539.5, the rural ratio saw a significant increase, reaching 661.7.

Recommendations

The imperative to undertake a thorough national population census to give researchers correct data on the population to study and project; for policymakers to make population-based decisions to achieve their national programs.

Directing the relevant departments to give multi-disciplinary data, namely, demographic data, and ensuring its easy access to the researchers for completion of their academic research.

Designation of specific staff within a public sector department in charge of data to categorize, collect, audit, and arrange the data in table format to be used as a reference data for researchers.

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